

Efficient NMPC strategies for thermal stress control of steam turbines [★]

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Abstract: This paper proposes an advanced control strategy for steam turbines characterized by frequent load variations based on a nonlinear model predictive control (NMPC) algorithm. In this specific scenario, turbines are subject to frequent variations in operating conditions and repeated start-ups that cause significant thermal stress. The main purpose of the developed NMPCs is to effectively regulate the generated electric power while limiting the rotor thermal stress. Collocation methods are adopted to improve the computation time required to solve the optimal control problem and then compared with a standard multiple-shooting approach. The proposed formulation includes time-varying constraints and nonlinear disturbances that vary within the prediction horizon of the dynamic module of the controller.

Keywords: Nonlinear model predictive control, Advanced control, Collocation methods, Optimal control, Rotor stress control.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the current energy market, power generation plants require an increasingly high level of flexibility, as well as the ability to handle discontinuous operations. Compared to traditional applications, steam turbines employed in modern power generation plants, such as Concentrated Solar Power Plants (CSPs) or Combined Cycle Power Plants (CCPPs), are subject to more frequent load variations. In the CSP case, these variations are mainly dependent on the site weather conditions, whereas, in the case of CCPPs, the variations are due to different plant operation strategies (i.e., from base load to peak load follower). A typical challenge of STs operating in such discontinuous scenarios is that these machines are subject to thermal stress, induced by cyclic start-ups and continuous load variations, deeply affecting the allowed energy production per day (Bucciarelli et al., 2020). The amount of this stress, particularly affecting the turbine rotor, is mainly related to changes in temperature and flow rate of the steam.

In this study, a CSP is considered, which represents one of the well-established solar-based technologies that play a major role in addressing present and future electricity problems (Baharoon et al., 2015). CSPs exploit high-temperature heat produced by solar collectors to generate electric power. To this aim, high-temperature steam is produced and sent to steam turbines (STs) where thermal

energy is converted into mechanical work and finally into electricity. STs are machines comprised of several pairs of stationary (stator) and rotating (rotor) blade rows. They can be classified into different categories depending on the criterion used, e.g., according to the initial and final conditions of the employed steam (Reddy et al., 2014). Multi-stage turbines typically consist of multiple pressure levels: high (HP), medium (MP), and low pressure (LP), each characterized by different inlet steam pressure.

Specific control systems have been investigated and designed for limiting rotor stress (Banaszkiewicz, 2016), with the major scope of optimizing the start-up phases (Faille and Davelaar, 2009). Recently, the benefits brought by the application of an online block for rotor stress monitoring have been demonstrated by Bucciarelli et al. (2020) and a control strategy based on Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC) has been implemented (Dettori et al., 2021). Nevertheless, issues are represented by a high computational burden such that the proposed Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) algorithm is not competitive with proprietary nonlinear optimization solvers, thus limiting its applicability to the use of proprietary software and impacting project economics.

The present paper is thus aimed at developing a suitable NMPC algorithm able to constrain the rotor thermal stress and control the power generated by a steam turbine in CSP with limited computational costs. The case study comprises a detailed nonlinear model and time-varying constraints on the output and the control action represented by nonlinear external disturbances, both demanding substantial computational resources. As an algo-

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rithm, the open-source MPC-code (Vaccari et al., 2023) is adopted; this tool is written in *Python* and exploits CasADi as a symbolic framework and IPOPT as nonlinear programming solver. Significant improvements and suitable adaptations for the specific case study are evaluated, namely by introducing collocation methods to solve the optimal control problem which allows a further reduction of computational costs while keeping a good level of accuracy (Tamimi and Li, 2009).

The remainder of the paper unfolds as follows: Section 2 details the models and methods employed, while Section 3 presents the obtained results, spanning from open-loop analysis to closed-loop simulations. Finally, concluding remarks are drawn in Section 4.

2. MODELS AND METHODS

The mathematical model for the dynamics of the steam turbine comprises two main components: one for the rotor temperature and the other for the thermal stress, as detailed later. Firstly, the overall system is outlined.

2.1 Model dimensions

A scheme of the considered steam turbine (ST) is shown in Figure 1. The following variables are included:

- **one input** (u): the wheel chamber pressure P_{wch} , that is, the first-stage region pressure;
- **two outputs** (y): the rotor stress σ and the generated electric power W ;
- $N_r + 1$ **states** (x): i.e., the rotor temperatures T , from the core to the skin, used in the spatial discretization.
- **three external disturbances** (d): the inlet steam pressure P_{in} , the inlet steam temperature T_{steam} , and the outlet steam pressure P_{out} .

Fig. 1. Scheme of the considered ST with main variables.

It is worth noting that the manipulated variable is subject to two time-varying constraints; the wheel chamber pressure is indeed bounded as follows: $P_{out} \leq P_{wch} \leq P_{in}$.

2.2 Thermal model

The thermal dynamics of the ST rotor can be described in cylindrical coordinates by using the following partial differential equation (PDE) with partial derivatives of temperature T with respect to time t and radius r :

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(kr \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) \quad (1)$$

The system is subjected to two boundary conditions:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} |_{r=0} = 0 \\ -k \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} |_{r=R} = HTC(t)(T(t)|_{r=R} - T_b(t)) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

and a suitable initial condition. Among physical parameters of the rotor steel, ρ is the density [kg/m^3], C_p is the heat capacity [$\text{J}/(\text{kg K})$], HTC is the global heat transfer coefficient [$\text{W}/(\text{m}^2 \text{K})$] and k is the thermal conductivity [$\text{W}/(\text{m K})$]. Finally, T_b is the bulk temperature, i.e., the steam temperature relevant to the convection phenomenon and R is the external rotor radius.

The radial domain is then evenly discretized over $N_r + 1$ nodes so that the spatial partial derivatives are reduced to ordinary ones with an explicit finite difference scheme:

$$\frac{\partial T_i}{\partial r} = \frac{T_{i+1} - T_{i-1}}{2\Delta r}; \quad \frac{\partial^2 T_i}{\partial r^2} = \frac{T_{i+1} - 2T_i + T_{i-1}}{\Delta r^2} \quad (3)$$

with $\Delta r = r_{i+1} - r_i$. Thus, after few steps, the following expression for the ordinary time derivative can be achieved:

$$\frac{dT_i}{dt} = \frac{k}{\rho C_p r_i} \frac{T_{i+1} - T_{i-1}}{2\Delta r} + \frac{k}{\rho C_p} \frac{T_{i+1} - 2T_i + T_{i-1}}{\Delta r^2} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) is obtained, subject to the following two boundary conditions, as reported in (Nakai et al., 1995):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dT_0}{dt} = 4 \frac{k}{\rho C_p} \frac{T_1 - T_0}{\Delta r^2} \\ \frac{dT_{N_r}}{dt} = \frac{1}{\rho C_p} \frac{1}{R\Delta r^2} (0.5k_r(2R + \Delta r)(T_{N_r+1} - T_{N_r}) + 0.5k_l(R + r_{N_r-1})(T_{N_r-1} - T_{N_r})) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where T_{N_r+1} is the fictitious temperature evaluated as:

$$T_{N_r+1} = T_{N_r-1} - 2HTC \frac{\Delta r}{k_r} (T_{N_r} - T_b) \quad (6)$$

Note that all the physical properties are dependent on temperature; ρ , k , and C_p are estimated with standard polynomial functions and are evaluated at the central temperature, i.e. T_i ; k_r is estimated at T_{N_r} and k_l at the mean temperature between T_{N_r} and T_{N_r-1} . The other variables, such as the heat transfer coefficient HTC , the bulk temperature T_b , and also the generated power W are described by empirical static functions of the measured variables, that is, the inlet and outlet steam pressure, the inlet steam temperature, and the wheel chamber pressure, e.g., $HTC = f(P_{in}, P_{out}, T_{steam}, P_{wch})$. The corresponding coefficients are known and have been identified by previously routine plant data (Bucciarelli et al., 2020).

2.3 Stress model

Starting from the von Mises stress expression, one can estimate the dynamic equivalent stress on the rotor's external surface as follows:

$$\sigma(t) = \left[\frac{\beta E}{1 - \nu} \left(T(r, t)|_{r=R} - \frac{2}{R^2} \int_0^R T(r, t) r dr \right) \right] \quad (7)$$

where β is the thermal expansion coefficient [$1/^\circ\text{C}$], E is the Young modulus [MPa], and ν is the Poisson ratio of the rotor steel. These physical parameters are evaluated by using standard polynomial functions of the rotor surface temperature. The integral term in Eq. (7) can be numerically approximated at any time instant j using the following linear relation (Rusin et al., 2014):

$$\sigma^j = C \cdot T^j = [c_0 \dots c_{N_r}] [T_0 \dots T_{N_r}]_j' \quad (8)$$

where:

$$C = \frac{\beta E}{1 - \nu} \left[-\frac{\Delta r^2}{R^2}, -\frac{2r_1 \Delta r}{R^2}, \dots, -\frac{2r_{N_r-1} \Delta r}{R^2}, 1 - \frac{\Delta r}{R} \right]$$

Note that, with this approximation, when all the rotor node temperatures from 0 to N_r are equal, the stress assumes negative values close to zero (Nakai et al., 1995).

2.4 NMPC standard formulation

The continuous-time NMPC problem treated is as follows:

$$\min_{x(\cdot), u(\cdot)} \int_0^\tau \ell_c(x(t), u(t)) dt \quad \text{s.t.} \quad (9a)$$

$$x(0) = x_0^* \quad (9b)$$

$$\dot{x} = f_c(x(t), u(t)) \quad (9c)$$

$$H(x(t), u(t), t) \leq 0 \quad (9d)$$

in which the objective function $\ell_c(\cdot)$ is integrated over the prediction horizon τ , from the initial state $x_0^* \in R^{N_r+1}$ and subject to the inequality constraint function $H(\cdot)$. This function $H(\cdot)$ includes simple lower and upper bounds for power W and a nonlinear function involving a time-varying stress upper bound $\sigma_{ub}(t)$, suitably calculated. The standard discretization of Problem (9) involves the integration of both the rotor thermal model function f_c and ℓ_c over a finite number N of time steps. In this framework, one popular implementation of Problem (9) employs, as optimization variables, the sequences of states $\mathbf{x} := (x_0, x_1, \dots, x_N)$ and control actions $\mathbf{u} := (u_0, u_1, \dots, u_{N-1})$ simultaneously, describing the so-called *multiple shooting* method. The optimization problem is thus reformulated in discrete-time as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}} \sum_{\kappa=0}^{N-1} \ell(x_\kappa, u_\kappa) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad (10a)$$

$$x_0 = x_0^* \quad (10b)$$

$$x_{\kappa+1} = F(x_\kappa, u_\kappa), \quad \kappa = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (10c)$$

$$H(x_\kappa, u_\kappa, \kappa) \leq 0, \quad \kappa = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (10d)$$

where F is the integrated state map from f_c , and the running cost function ℓ is the approximation on each interval of the integral of ℓ_c .

2.5 Collocation methods

Collocation methods are the best-known class of direct transcription methods, for which the continuous-time state trajectory defined by (9c) is approximated by a polynomial function whose coefficients are determined simultaneously with the control trajectory (Puchaud et al., 2023). They can be formulated by two different representations: *derivative* and *state* representation (Rawlings et al., 2019). In the present work, the second approach is used, which implies the introduction of the *internal states* S_κ as additional optimization variables. Suitable equality constraints and the state update are employed to follow an implicit integration rule, where M is the order of the chosen integration method. In this work, the fourth-order Gauss-Legendre method is adopted, that is, $M = 2$ is set. The following equality constraints are added with respect to Problem (10):

$$G(x_\kappa, S_\kappa, u_\kappa) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\Delta t}(D_{11}(s_{\kappa 1} - x_i) + D_{12}(s_{\kappa 2} - x_\kappa)) - F(s_{\kappa 1}, u_\kappa) \\ \frac{1}{\Delta t}(D_{21}(s_{\kappa 1} - x_\kappa) + D_{22}(s_{\kappa 2} - x_\kappa)) - F(s_{\kappa 2}, u_\kappa) \end{bmatrix}$$

where Δt is the integration step, and $S_\kappa = [s_{\kappa 1}, s_{\kappa 2}]$ collects the two sequences of internal states, with $s_{\kappa l} \in R^{N_r+1}$. The transition to the next state is thus defined as:

Table 1. Butcher tableau of the 4th order Gauss-Legendre method.

$1/2 - \sqrt{3}/6$	$a_{11} = 1/4$	$a_{12} = 1/4 - \sqrt{3}/6$
$1/2 + \sqrt{3}/6$	$a_{21} = 1/4 + \sqrt{3}/6$	$a_{22} = 1/4$
		$b_1 = 1/2$
		$b_2 = 1/2$

$$x_{\kappa+1} = F_\kappa(x_\kappa, S_\kappa, u_\kappa) := x_\kappa + \tilde{b}_1(s_{\kappa 1} - x_\kappa) + \tilde{b}_2(s_{\kappa 2} - x_\kappa) \quad (11)$$

Note that the various coefficients derive from the Butcher tableau of the selected method, as shown in Table 1. In particular, a_{pl} and b_l are indeed elements of the tableau, with $b \in R^M$; D_{pl} compose the inverse matrix $D = A^{-1}$ from coefficients a_{pl} ; finally, \tilde{b}_l are the elements of vector \tilde{b} obtained as $D^T b$.

The running cost function ℓ_c is approximated on each interval by a weighted sum of its evaluation on the collocation time points, as in Eq. (12).

$$\int_{t_\kappa}^{t_{\kappa+1}} \ell_c(x(t), u(t)) dt = \sum_{\kappa=0}^{N-1} \ell(x_\kappa, S_\kappa, u_\kappa) \quad (12)$$

Thus still using a multiple shooting approach and inserting an additional set of optimization variables, that is, the internal states $\mathbf{S} := (S_0, S_1, \dots, S_{N-1})$, Problem (9) is thus reformulated as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{u}} \sum_{\kappa=0}^{N-1} \ell(x_\kappa, S_\kappa, u_\kappa) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad (13a)$$

$$x_0 = x_0^* \quad (13b)$$

$$x_{\kappa+1} = F_\kappa(x_\kappa, S_\kappa, u_\kappa), \quad \kappa = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (13c)$$

$$G(x_\kappa, S_\kappa, u_\kappa) = 0, \quad \kappa = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (13d)$$

$$H(x_\kappa, S_\kappa, u_\kappa, \kappa) \leq 0, \quad \kappa = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (13e)$$

Note that, since the state updating is performed through (11), it is not necessary to integrate the differential system at each iteration, hence, there is a considerable reduction of the computational costs (Song et al., 2023).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Open-loop analysis

To test the system dynamics, an open-loop (OL) simulation is first performed, with appropriate variations in manipulated and disturbance variables. The wheel chamber pressure (P_{wch}), steam temperature (T_{steam}), output pressure (P_{out}), and inlet pressure (P_{in}) are imposed as sinusoidal signals. The analysis explores the effect of an increased steam temperature by introducing an abrupt variation from an initial uniform rotor temperature.

The results obtained from the integration of the system Eqs. (4)-(5) are reported in Figure 2. The temperature profiles, with $N_r + 1 = 31$ states, grow at an increasing rate from the core to the skin of the rotor; note that for infinity time, the whole turbine rotor oscillates around the same stationary value given by the oscillating steam bulk temperature ($\bar{T}_b = 350^\circ\text{C}$). The stress induced by this temperature gradient exhibits a large initial increase but, since the steam temperature is not subject to large time variations, the rotor skin temperature tends to match the steam bulk temperature and then the rotor stress will

Fig. 2. OL simulation: trends and profiles of rotor temperature and stress in response to T_{steam} variation.

Fig. 3. Model block diagram of the considered STs.

approach close-to-zero values at infinity times, as shown on the right panel of Figure 2.

Note that the considered CSP includes two different types of steam turbines, one LP and one HP, which differ in terms of operating ranges and model parameters. The block diagram of the considered STs is shown in Figure 3, where f_1 , f_2 and f_3 are the empirical static functions for the estimation of HTC , W , and T_b , respectively. As can be observed, the stress dynamics (σ) is affected directly by the rotor temperature T , while the external inputs (P_{in} , T_{steam} , P_{out} , P_{wch}) have only an indirect influence filtered by the evolution of HTC and T_b .

Through a gain analysis, it is revealed that the stress undergoes a strong variation when T_{steam} is significantly different from the initial rotor temperature but is also influenced by the pressure variations for both LP and HP turbines. Note also that in the case of the LP turbine, T_b is not affected by the other disturbances, and by the manipulated variable P_{wch} , i.e., $T_b = T_{steam}$, thus impacting on the stress controllability. The relative gain (K_r) for W , HTC , T_b , and σ is determined by the ratio of the variation in the respective output (y) to the variation in one of the system inputs (u). The term ‘‘relative’’ denotes that each deviation is normalized against the corresponding average value, that is, $K_r = \frac{\Delta y / \bar{y}}{\Delta u / \bar{u}}$. In Table 2, we report the mean value of the relative gains ($\overline{K_r}$) with associated standard deviation (Std_{K_r}).

The results showcase the effects of maintaining the three disturbances constant while linearly varying the manipulated variable (P_{wch}). Notably, in the LP case, the order of magnitude of the σ gain is lower than that of the HP case. This suggests that, besides the zero influence of P_{wch} on T_b , the impact of the control action on the stress, via HTC and then T , is reduced. Note that the stress variation is mostly linked with the difference between the initial rotor temperature and the imposed T_b ; in fact, by removing the

Table 2. Mean value of relative gains with respect to P_{wch} and its standard deviation.

Turbine		W	HTC	T_b	σ
LP	$\overline{K_r}$	1.134	0.867	0	0.217
	Std_{K_r}	0.04	0.011	0	1.3
HP	$\overline{K_r}$	2.203	1.298	0.133	1.111
	Std_{K_r}	0.178	0.096	0.039	3.58

first 100 samples of simulation, characterized by a large temperature gradient, mean gain values reduce from 0.217 to 0.111 (with $Std_{K_r} = 0.53$) and from 1.111 to 0.846 (with $Std_{K_r} = 1.94$) for the LP and HP turbines, respectively.

Nevertheless, the action exerted by P_{wch} on the stress is observed in both cases; this means that there are sufficient conditions for the success of the controller, provided that, to achieve its aim, it is not necessary to overcome the physical constraints of pressure. Therefore, monitoring stress becomes crucial to prevent it from surpassing the designated upper bound, serving as a safety measure. With an understanding of the model’s inherent challenges, the next step involves testing the proposed NMPCs in a comprehensive closed-loop analysis.

3.2 Closed-loop simulations

MPC-code¹ aims to be a resource as general as possible, by enclosing the most common cases, and for this reason, is continuously under development (Vaccari et al., 2023). To this aim, the available version on *GitHub* now includes the suitable changes made for the case study in question. Below, the specific settings adopted are briefly reported, illustrating the modules used composing the algorithm for both Problems (10) and (13).

- **State Estimator:** given the non-linear nature of the case study, the employed estimator is the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF), with $Q_{kf} = 10^{-5}I_{N_r+1}$, $R_{kf} = 10^{-4}I_2$, $P_0 = I_{N_r+1}$, which are the covariance matrices for process and measurement noises, and initial state error, respectively.
- **Dynamic Optimization:** it includes the difference between the actual and set-point values (y_{sp}) of the output $y = F_y(x, u, d)$, weighted by matrix Q , as well as the input variations by matrix S , over N as follows:

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{\kappa=0}^{N-1} \ell(x_{\kappa}, u_{\kappa}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\kappa=0}^{N-1} \left[(y_{\kappa} - y_{sp})' Q (y_{\kappa} - y_{sp}) + (u_{\kappa} - u_{\kappa-1})' S (u_{\kappa} - u_{\kappa-1}) \right] \quad (14)$$

where u_{-1} is known and as tuning we set $Q = \text{diag}(0, 1)$, $S = 0.6$, and $N = 35$. Note that there is no requirement to track a stress set-point, so a proper selection of parameters in Q allows the power to closely follow its reference; simultaneously, the impact of the matrix S ensures minimal fluctuations in the manipulated variable, preventing unnecessary stress on the control valve.

Closed-loop simulations are executed with sinusoidal signals representing the three external disturbances (P_{in} , T_{steam} , P_{out}), with periodic variations extended across the prediction horizon. Note that this scenario does not intend

¹ <https://github.com/CPCLAB-UNIFI/MPC-code/wiki>

Table 3. Deviation in the responses: multiple shooting vs. collocation method.

Turbine	NRMSE $\times 10^6$			
	P_{wch}	σ	W	T_{30}
LP	5.93	2.27	4.95	0.322
HP	2.32	2.10	2.61	1.23

Table 4. Computational times in seconds: multiple shooting vs. collocation method.

Turbine	Method	Min	Max	Mean	Std
LP	MS	4.26	9.67	5.93	1.06
	CM	0.41	0.95	0.50	0.07
HP	MS	6.61	11.33	8.16	0.76
	CM	0.53	1.48	0.65	0.12

to emulate a typical industrial steam turbine start-up, but it is well-suited for the validation of the developed NMPCs in an even more challenging scenario. The simulated case is the nominal one, with no plant/model mismatch and no need for a disturbance model. The optimal control problem adheres to the physical constraints outlined in Section 2.1, corresponding to time-varying nonlinear disturbances.

Finally, the solution derived from the traditional multiple shooting (MS) method, as detailed in Problem (10), is compared with that obtained using the collocation method (CM), as in Problem (13). The corresponding normalized outputs are depicted in Figure 4. The percentage values for power reflect the desired set-point level, while stress percentages are relative to the upper bound (σ_{ub}). As can be observed, thermal stress is kept under its upper bound for both turbines, while the power set-point can be tracked only for the LP turbine. In addition, the various time trends are almost overlapping for the two tested methods. To better quantify the difference between corresponding signals, a Normalized Root Mean Square Error (NRMSE) is computed, specifically for the input (P_{wch}), the two outputs (σ, W), and the last state (T_{30}), representing the rotor skin temperature:

$$NRMSE = \frac{1}{\bar{y}^{MS}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{\kappa=0}^{N_s} (y_{\kappa}^{MS} - y_{\kappa}^{CM})^2} \quad (15)$$

where y_{κ} are the values of the generic variable obtained by multiple-shooting (MS) and collocation method (CM), \bar{y}^{MS} is the mean value for MS, and N_s is the number of samples. Table 3 shows the numerical results for both cases, LP and HP turbine. The obtained values can be considered acceptable since the largest one, related to P_{wch} for LP turbine, is less than $6 \cdot 10^{-6}$. This means that the proposed collocation method proves to be an excellent approximation of the solution obtained with the traditional MS approach.

Another important result concerns the computational time required by the two methods (on a PC equipped with Intel Core i7-8565U CPU, 1.80 GHz, 16 GB RAM). In particular, Table 4 shows the times per iteration: minimum, maximum, and mean values and corresponding standard deviations are reported. As in both cases, a 92% time reduction is obtained, the proposed CM shows to highly outperform the standard MS, and, since the control

(a) Stress in time

(b) Power in time

Fig. 4. Output time trends: multiple shooting vs. collocation method.

sampling time is equal to 1 second, CM proves the only method implementable online.

3.3 Stress limitation

To verify that the designed NMPCs are indeed capable of keeping the stress values below the imposed constraints, a second set of closed-loop simulations was performed by keeping the same conditions described in Section 3.2 and by lowering ($\simeq -25\%$) the stress upper bound (σ_{ub}) with respect to the previous values used for Figure 4. Only results for the collocation method are illustrated below.

The time trends of the normalized stress, control action, and power, in two cases (LP and HP turbines) are shown in Figure 5. It can be seen how the controller manages to prevent the stress from overpassing the new upper bound for both turbines. The corresponding effect of P_{wch} is well visible; in particular, in the case of the LP turbine, the control action undergoes a significant reduction, moving away from the stationary condition close to the upper bound (P_{in}), a value that guarantees a good tracking of the power set-point. On the other hand, for the HP turbine, P_{wch} keeps close to its upper bounds, but the power set-point is not achieved.

For the HP turbine, when we refer to the previous Figure 4, the stress increases significantly in the initial times until reaches a maximum and then relaxes. When the stress upper bound is reduced, the controller behavior is different. By zooming Figure 5, a minor constraint violation on the stress is indeed registered at about $t = 55s$. Therefore, the input is not updated but kept constant at the previous feasible value. Note that this scenario could cause also a violation of the physical constraints on the pressure, but in this case, the P_{wch} remains within its operating range and the power fails to reach its reference while settling at a lower stationary value. As a matter of fact, the adoption of slack variables within the optimization problem could solve this issue, at the expense of some additional computational

Fig. 5. Trends of stress (top), pressure (middle), and power (bottom) with relative bounds.

costs. To sum up, the designed NMPCs prove to guarantee the limitation of the thermal stress of the rotor, and when feasible also track the power set-point.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we developed NMPCs for steam turbines operating in concentrated solar plants. The final goal is achieving effective electric power control while ensuring compliance with imposed physical constraints on rotor thermal stress and wheel chamber pressure, even under time-varying operating conditions. The use of collocation methods for the dynamic optimization problem has substantially reduced computational costs, providing solutions closely aligned with those obtained through a conventional multiple-shooting approach. As a general remark, constraining the rotor stress by only manipulating the wheel chamber pressure proves a challenging task as the control problem shows limited feasibility regions. Additional limitations would also arise by considering that the thermal exchange must not decrease under a safety threshold related to the trip condition of the turbine or the damage of other mechanical components. Therefore, it is crucial to monitor stress for optimizing startup procedures and maintenance intervals, thereby extending equipment life. This turns into the necessity of combining the stress monitoring-based NMPC with other good operability practices as the attemperation of the steam input temperature.

As a future research direction, an enhancement of the turbine model appears desirable, aiming for a closer relationship between the wheel chamber pressure and the thermal stress or introducing an additional input that more significantly affects the stress. Other upcoming ef-

forts will involve establishing a correlation between wheel chamber pressure and throttling valve stroke, allowing valve opening to serve as the manipulated variable, and then optimizing both HP and LP turbines simultaneously, to resemble a more realistic industrial scenario.

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